

Report of the CORDEX Task Force on Regional Ocean Modelling and Climate Projections

Somot S.¹, Melet A.², Drenkard E.³, Estrada S.⁴, Herrmann M.⁵, Holt J.⁶, Iovino D.⁷,
Meier H. E. M.⁸, Orr A.⁹, Thatcher M.¹⁰, Urakawa S.¹¹, Zhang X.¹²

Affiliations :

¹ CNRM, Météo-France, France

² Mercator Ocean International, France

³ GFDL, NOAA, USA

⁴ CICESE, Mexico

⁵ LEGOS, France & USTH, Vietnam & Chulalongkorn University, Thailand

⁶ NOC, UK

⁷ CMCC, Italy

⁸ IOW, Germany

⁹ BAS, UK

¹⁰ MRI, Japan Meteorological Agency, Japan

¹¹ CSIRO, Australia

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List of acronyms

AR7	IPCC 7th Assessment Report
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CPM	Convection-Permitting Modelling (e.g. as in TF-CPM)
CPRCM	Convection-permitting regional climate model
COWCLIP	Coordinated Ocean Wave Climate Project
DR	Data Request
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
FPS	CORDEX Flagship Pilot Study
GCM	Global Climate Model
ML	Machine Learning
OMDP	CLIVAR Ocean Model Development Panel
ORCM	Ocean Regional Climate Model
POC	CORDEX Point of Contact
RCM	Regional climate model
REF	CMIP Rapid Evaluation Framework
SAT	CORDEX Science Advisory Team
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathway
TF	CORDEX Task Force

Document version history

Version	Comment
2025-11-13	Initial version shared with the SAT for comments

1. Introduction

Following the CORDEX ICRC in September 2023 and its D1 session called “CORDEX-Ocean: Towards a CORDEX framework for Ocean Regional Climate Modelling” as well as internal discussions in CLIVAR OMDP (Climate Variability Ocean Model Development Panel), a joint CORDEX – CLIVAR-OMDP task force has been established in Summer 2024 (<https://cordex.org/strategic-activities/taskforces/task-force-on-regional-ocean-climate-projections/>) and officially launched by CORDEX on December 3rd 2024. The TF is to develop a strategic plan for a longer-term WCRP initiative which will aim to:

- Coordinate regional ocean climate projections (physics, biogeochemistry, sea-ice) worldwide by developing coordinated simulation protocols and by delivering standardized datasets
- Advance the science of regional ocean climate modelling and projections, including through multi-model assessments, identification of robust biases and underlying processes
- Engage a large community of regional ocean modelers and model users to provide a forum for sharing knowledge and experience across domains
- Serve the climate impact and adaptation needs by engaging with relevant users/stakeholders and by providing data and expertise to ocean climate services
- Contribute to expert assessment reports (e.g., IPCC-AR7, national or regional assessment reports)

The goal of the current document is to synthesize the work of the TF so far and to detail the strategic vision and plan for a long-term initiative on regional ocean climate modelling and projections within the WCRP.

2. Task Force functioning

We present here the functioning of the TF during its 1.5 years of existence.

2.1 Member appointment

Initially, the CORDEX SAT nominates Samuel Somot and CLIVAR OMDP nominates Angélique Melet to initiate the TF and to propose member and co-leader names. The members of the TF were proposed to cover a diversity of geographical areas, ocean science expertise, and career development stages, keeping a balance between CORDEX-originated and CLIVAR-originated persons. One representative of OMDP and of CORDEX SAT were also included to secure a good connection with the mother panels. In a

2nd step, the TF members decided to nominate A. Melet and S. Somot as TF co-coordinators. The list of members is the following:

- [Co-coordinator: Angélique Melet](#), Mercator Ocean International, France. Northeastern Atlantic Ocean, Physics, Sea Level. Link to CMEMS and CLIVAR OMDP
- [Co-coordinator: Samuel Somot](#), CNRM, Météo-France, France, Mediterranean Sea, Physics, Coupling. Link to Med-CORDEX and EURO-CORDEX
- [Marine Herrmann](#), LEGOS, France & USTH, Vietnam & Chulalongkorn University, Thailand, South-East Asia, Physics, Biogeochemistry. Link to CORDEX-SEA
- [Sheila Estrada](#), CICESE, Mexico. Gulf of Mexico, Pacific Coast, Caribbean Sea, Physics, Biogeochemistry, Wave, Coupling, Link to CORDEX-CAM
- [Markus Meier](#), IOW, Germany. Baltic Sea, North Sea, Physics, Biogeochemistry, Sea-Ice, Paleo-oceanography. Link to Baltic Earth
- [Andrew Orr](#), BAS, UK. Polar regions, Physics. Link to Polar-CORDEX
- [Dorotea Iovino](#), CMCC, Italy. Global ocean. Co-chair of CLIVAR OMDP. Link to CLIVAR OMDP and to CLIVAR NORP and SORP
- [Shogo Urakawa](#), MRI, Japan Meteorological Agency, Japan. Japan coastal area, Physics. Link to CLIVAR OMDP
- [Jason Holt](#), NOC, UK. European North-West Shelf, North Atlantic/Arctic, Physics, Biogeochemistry, Wave. Link to FLAME
- [Xuebin \(Chubin\) Zhang](#), CSIRO, Australia. Australian coastal zone, China Sea, Physics, Biogeochemistry, Marine ecosystems, Sea Level. Link to CLIVAR Pacific Regional Panel
- [Elizabeth Drenkard](#), GFDL, NOAA, USA. Northeast Pacific, Physics, Marine ecosystems
- [Marcus Thatcher](#), CSIRO, Australia. Member of the CORDEX SAT. Link to CORDEX

2.2 Regular Meetings

The TF met regularly, with about 1 meeting every 3 months in visioconference (4 September 2024, 6 November 2024, 9 January 2025, 25 March 2025, 1 July 2025, 12 September 2025). Subgroup meetings on targeted activities were also organized. We did not have the opportunity to meet face-to-face. Meetings were prepared and organized by the 2 TF coordinators with an active contribution from the individual members. They were used to refine the TF definition, to share a common vision of the TF goals, to recall the CLIVAR-OMPD and CORDEX-SAT objectives, to prepare the contribution of the regional

ocean climate community to the forthcoming IPCC-AR7, to make a list of actions and to review it regularly.

2.3 Communication

A central SharePoint hosted by Mercator and managed by A. Melet was adopted for the TF work and 2 emailing lists hosted by Météo-France were created, one for the TF tf-future-regional-ocean@meteo.fr and one for the general community interested by the initiative future-regional-ocean@meteo.fr

For external members, quick description of the TF can be found on web pages, hosted by CORDEX and by CLIVAR-OMDP:

<https://cordex.org/strategic-activities/taskforces/task-force-on-regional-ocean-climate-projections/>

<https://clivar.org/clivar-omdpriifs-cordex-task-team-regional-ocean-climate-projections>.

2.4 Interactions with CORDEX and CLIVAR communities

During the TF lifetime, the contact with CORDEX SAT and CLIVAR OMDP was regular, allowing not to diverge from the vision of the two umbrella bodies.

The interactions with the CORDEX community were done during the CORDEX SAT in-person meeting in Santander (Sept 2024), at the on-line open SAT meetings and at various multi-TF meetings, in particular with the TF-CORDEX-CMIP7.

The connection with CLIVAR-OMDP meeting was secured through discussion at the OMDP meetings as various members of the TF are also members of this panel (D. Iovino, A. Melet, S. Urugawa). Regional ocean climate projections have been listed as a new activity of OMDP since 2025. The TF activities were also presented at the pan-CLIVAR meeting in September 2025 with a keynote presentation during the Symposium but also in cross-panels meetings (including with NORP and SORP, GSOP, and planned for later with PRP).

3. Motivations for a new WCRP initiative on Regional Ocean Climate Modelling and Projections

The first task accomplished by the TF was to list the motivations for a potential coordination of the worldwide efforts in studying future regional ocean evolution and

therefore to consolidate the potential need for launching a new WCRP initiative on Regional Ocean Climate Modelling and Projections.

3.1 Scientific motivations:

- Climate change is strongly altering the ocean with adverse effects such as rising temperature and sea levels, loss of sea ice, ocean acidification, change in connectivity, marine heatwaves and de-oxygenation (IPCC, 2021). Characterizing climate change's effects on the regional ocean, regional seas or coastal zones at spatial and temporal scales relevant for society and decision making becomes increasingly urgent.
- Change in the regional to coastal ocean state (e.g. mean sea surface temperature, marine heatwaves) can influence surrounding land areas through land-sea contrast modifications, humidity and heat advection, change in atmosphere stability or cloud cover (Somot et al. 2008, Gonzalez et al. 2025). Considering regional oceanic changes in CORDEX-like regional climate models is therefore particularly relevant for territories such as coastal regions or islands and even in some cases for areas far from the ocean as the ocean can mitigate or amplify local climate change signals.
- Ocean dynamics span a wide range of scales, including small-scale structures (e.g. eddies, jets, fronts, currents, semi-permanent meso-scale structures, strait, overflows, open-sea deep convection, upwelling) that can affect regionally and locally the ocean circulation, temperature, salinity, sea level, sea ice or chlorophyll pattern. Therefore, spatio-temporal high-resolution representation of oceanic areas, driven by relevant forcings at the right scale (atmosphere, aerosol deposition, river discharges, tides, boundary currents...) are required to represent regional ocean and its future evolution.
- Model uncertainty also exists for ocean models (Darmaraki et al. 2019, Parras-Berrocal et al. 2024) and various regional ocean models will represent climate change signal differently even forced by the same large-scale forcings. This calls for a coordinated multi-model initiative to cover this key source of uncertainty in future climate projections.

3.2 Impact motivations:

- Ocean climatic impacts drivers (CIDs, i.e. physical climate system conditions that affect an element of society or ecosystems) can induce widespread risks and tremendous impacts worldwide, especially in coastal zones (IPCC, 2022). Indeed, coastal areas experience higher concentration of population, marine ecosystems and assets: almost 1 billion people currently live in low-elevation (<10m) coastal zones globally (Reimann et al., 2023) and the fast-growing ocean economy was estimated to \$2.6 trillion in 2020 (OECD, 2025).
- Characterizing regional ocean change allows to provide precious knowledge and data to a large variety of climate data users, interested by relevant sectorial impacts such as aquaculture, fisheries, ecosystem conservation, tourism, maritime transport, recreational activities, energy production, health, not well served by currently available climate change dataset.
- Humans and marine ecosystems live everywhere along the coast all around the planet. Focusing on some key areas is not an option, and global coverage of localized climate change information for the ocean and coastal areas should be envisaged.

3.3 Structural motivations:

- Climate projections of the marine environment are currently mostly generated using global climate models (GCMs, e.g. from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, CMIP). However, the latest generation of GCMs (CMIP6) and even the next one (CMIP7) remains too coarse to represent ocean processes relevant for regional seas or coastal zones (e.g. Hewitt et al. 2022) and finally to support effective decision-making in regions and localities (Fig 1).
- A few high-resolution global coupled climate models has been recently developed (HighResMIP, Haarsma et al., 2016; Roberts et al., 2025 and DestinE, Doblas-Reyes et al. in discussion), but most climate models will not reach a sufficient spatial resolution (typically $1/10^\circ$ or more in the ocean and in the atmosphere), the VHR-GCM are still in their infancy and their model configuration cannot be adapted to regional or local ocean specificities. Moreover, these models often lack processes crucial in the coastal ocean, e.g. tides or detailed bottom boundary layer interactions.
- To provide refined regional-to-local information on ocean past, present, and future CIDs, GCMs can be downscaled using process-based ocean regional (limited-area) climate models (ORCMs, coupled to or forced by an atmospheric model). Compared to GCMs, ORCMs benefit from increased spatial resolution, more

tailored model configurations for the area of interest (e.g., choice of coordinates, choice and calibration of parameterizations, addition of relevant processes), and the possibility to bias-correct forcings from GCMs. Ocean climate downscaling started about 20 years ago with ocean-forced (Thorpe and Bigg 2000, Döscher and Meier 2004, Somot et al. 2006) or coupled models (Döscher et al. 2002,, Aldrian et al. 2005, Somot et al. 2008) and is currently a dynamic research area covering different regions around the world (e.g., Drenkard et al. 2021, Holt et al. 2025 for reviews). However, such initiatives lack international coordination and efforts so far have been highly fragmented, primarily focused on research purposes with each group using a different approach to scenario and CMIP model selections, experimental design, applications and validation.

- On the contrary, regional atmospheric climate projections are coordinated through the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX, Giorgi et al., 2009), under the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) Regional Information for Society (RIfS) core project. However, CORDEX has mostly focused so far on the atmosphere and land, with only a few CORDEX regions including the coupling with ocean models (mostly Med-CORDEX, Arctic CORDEX).

Figure 1. From global climate models to regional ocean climate models. The schematic illustrates the refinement of models meshes, the increased complexity of regional models (variables, components) and some climate risks and blue economy markets. Source: Mercator Ocean International

3.4 Towards a worldwide regional ocean climate change assessment

Considering the motivations identified above, the first TF meetings allowed us to identify 3 needs related to the regional ocean future climate projections. A list of bullet points was developed by the TF to help designing future climate change assessments of the ocean regions.

- **Assess the past and future evolution of the ocean state at the regional scale, including in vulnerable areas (e.g. regional seas, coastal zones, islands, coastal cities, inland seas) for various variables, including existing and new Climate-Impact-Drivers.** Ocean regions are poorly addressed in the regional information chapters of AR6–WGI (chap 10, 11, 12, Atlas) and in the AR6 Interactive Atlas. There is a growing need for regional to local climate information by stakeholders interested in specific regions of the ocean. In the AR6 Interactive Atlas, climate change projections in ocean regions are assessed only with CMIP simulations except for the Mediterranean Sea for which CMIP and CORDEX simulations are provided.
- **Evaluate the quality of regional ocean models and regional ocean projections for delivering climate information for the oceanic regions at the relevant spatial scale.** So far, most of the literature assessed in the AR6–WGI for the oceanic regions comes from GCMs including low resolution ocean models. Those model configurations are known to be irrelevant to assess many of the world’s oceanic regions, such as the semi-enclosed seas or shallow coastal zones. In addition, important regional ocean processes can be explicitly resolved (e.g., tides, surges) or more accurately parameterized in regional ocean models. More complex and regionally calibrated biogeochemical or sea-ice models can also be used at regional scales.
- **Assess the past and future evolution of ocean phenomena relevant for society and decision-making at the relevant spatio-temporal scales such as oceanic extremes (e.g. marine heatwaves, extreme sea level, reversal of surface circulation, ocean dense water formation, sea-ice extent minimum, eutrophication...).** Ocean contains small-scale phenomena relevant for their potential impacts on marine ecosystems and human maritime activities. Substantial progress has been made in monitoring, modelling, and understanding those phenomena over the last years. Future assessment reports such as AR7 can therefore rely on recent literature to assess those phenomena and their evolution under climate change.

3. Strategic vision

Considering the scientific, impact and structural motivations listed above, the TF developed the following strategic vision:

- The Regional Ocean Climate Projections community is now mature to develop and carry out a worldwide and long-term coordinated initiative within WCRP to strengthen its knowledge production and its impact on other branches of climate science and on society.
- To our knowledge, the most adapted organizational instrument would be a

WCRP “**Regional Ocean Climate Projections Working Group (WG)**”, under the umbrella of both the CLIVAR OMDP and CORDEX SAT

with the following Terms of reference.

The WG objectives are to:

- **Coordinate regional ocean climate projections** (physics, biogeochemistry, sea-ice) worldwide by developing coordinated simulation protocols for both ocean-only and coupled RCMs, and by delivering standardized datasets
- **Explore the potential of data-driven machine-learning approaches** to simulate oceanic regions and their future evolution, strengthening the promising training opportunities given by the datasets produced with physics- and biology-based models
- **Advance the science of regional ocean climate modelling and projections**, including through multi-model assessments, identification of robust biases and underlying processes
- **Engage a large community of regional ocean modelers and model users** to provide a forum for sharing knowledge and experience across domains
- **Serve the climate impact and adaptation needs** by engaging with relevant users/stakeholders and by providing data and expertise to ocean climate services
- **Contribute to expert assessment reports** (e.g., IPCC-AR7, national or regional assessment reports)

The strategic vision of a “Regional ocean climate projections WG” rooted in both CLIVAR OMDP and RfS CORDEX is supported by the following:

- **CLIVAR OMDP** brings its long-term knowledge on ocean model development, including tuning, spinup and parameterization development, on climate variability and change over the ocean and on air-sea interactions.
- **Rifs CORDEX** brings its long-term experience in worldwide coordination of regional climate modelling initiative, its capacity to produce coordinated climate projection datasets and its strong connection with stakeholders, climate services and, more generally, regional climate data users for the benefice of society

The structure of the WG includes:

- Two co-chairs, one nominated by CLIVAR OMDP and one nominated by CORDEX SAT
- A list of 10–20 WG members for the, nominated by the CLIVAR OMDP and CORDEX SAT bodies after a community open call from the WCRP (as done for CLIVAR panels or the recent CORDEX-CMIP7 Task Team for instance)
- A CLIVAR OMDP member and a CORDEX SAT member to ensure the coordination of the WG activities with the OMDP and SAT long-term vision and overall objectives
- A larger community of interest, open to members of the regional ocean modelling community or to the ocean climate projection users

The WG will report to CLIVAR OMDP and to CORDEX SAT on an annual basis or when requested and will help bring the two entities closer together. Rotation of the chairs and of the members will follow WCRP rules.

We acknowledge that this initiative will take time to fully develop and will not be fully operational in 2026 or to contribute to IPCC-AR7. Therefore, we propose a 2-step implementation plan:

- **Transition phase in 2026:** transition phase to allow time for constructive interactions between CLIVAR OMDP and CORDEX SAT to approve the terms of reference, to prepare the community open call for membership and to start fast track actions allowing to meet the IPCC-AR7 deadlines (see section 4). Each current TF member will decide to continue or not to serve the WG activities during this transition period.
- **Maturity phase from 2027 onwards:** longer-term implementation plan to reach a mature stage for the WG. This phase will target the downscaling of CMIP7 models through coordinated protocols, multi-model assessment studies, and a wider contribution to future regional assessment reports on climate change and the ocean (e.g., IPCC AR8)

4. Transition Phase in 2026: Fast track actions

In addition to the structure of the WG and the call for membership, the transition year will serve to develop Fast Track actions to contribute to IPCC-AR7 with the existing material.

4.1 The TF Position paper

The TF is currently preparing a position paper to justify the action and to argue for the development and use of regionally downscaled ocean climate simulations. This paper, led by A. Melet and co-authored by all members of the TF, will be submitted to the CORDEX 15-year anniversary special issue in PlosOne, by the end of 2025.

4.2 Inventory of the existing regional ocean climate projections

One of the targeted contribution to IPCC-AR7 is the provision of published studies based on downscaled ocean climate projections for the regional chapters and of related datasets for the IPCC Interactive Atlas with ready-to-use regional ocean climate projections as was done with the Med-CORDEX regional ocean projections for instance in Chapter 12 of WG1 and in the AR6 Interactive Atlas. To achieve this and knowing that we will not be able to develop a fully coordinated initiative in due course, we decided to rely on existing simulations. Therefore, the TF launched a worldwide survey on existing regional ocean projections. This activity was coordinated by E. Drenkard.

The survey results are currently under analysis; they will be synthesized in the TF position paper and will serve task 4.3.

Figure 2: Domains of existing regionally downscaled ocean climate projections based on the task force inventory, for the physical ocean in blue and the marine biogeochemistry.

4.3 Minimal standardization of the existing simulations

Based on the survey results, we consider that we have enough existing simulations and associated publications with good enough spatial coverage (for ocean physics at least) to allow a potential contribution to AR7 and its Interactive Atlas with this weakly-coordinated ensemble. Therefore, we will propose in the coming months a minimal standardization process of a limited number of variables to the data producers in order (1) to develop fast track multi-model multi-domain studies for a selection of ocean climatic impact drivers before the AR7 deadlines and (2) to provide standardized datasets to the IPCC Interactive Atlas planned in WGI and WGII if requested during the assessment. In the current TF, S. Somot is leading this activity.

Here is an example of regional ocean climate files, already produced in the Med-CORDEX framework, adapting the CORDEX-CMIP6 archive specifications to ocean variables:

```
tos_MED-12_CNRM-ESM2-1_ssp585_r1i1p1f2_CNRM_CNRM-RCSM6B-SN_v1-  
r1_day_20260101-20301231.nc
```

4.4 Proposing new reference regions for regional ocean assessment

Another key aspect of regional climate assessment in the IPCC report is the domain definition on which the assessment is performed. Regional boxes over land were proposed initially by F. Giorgi based on climate classification and climate change signal and are relatively well adapted to CORDEX regional domains. However, this is not the case for the regional domains used in AR6 for the assessment of the regions of the ocean. We are therefore currently working on proposing new reference regions for the ocean and coastal zones to improve regional climate change assessment worldwide for the various regional seas, coastal zones, and small islands.

This activity is currently led by A. Melet in the TF and will contribute to the TF position paper. It was also presented to the CLIVAR community during its pan-CLIVAR meeting and symposium in September 2025 to collect feedback from the ocean community.

5. Maturity Phase: from 2027 onwards

Our vision is that the regional ocean climate initiative will be fully mature only in a few years, hopefully in time for the downscaling of CMIP7 or CMIP8 Assessment Fast Track (AFT) and a more coordinated contribution to IPCC-AR8. We list here the actions required to fully develop this initiative.

5.1 Preparing a strongly coordinated initiative for the downscaling of CMIP7 GCM

Organizing the community to prepare in a coordinated way the downscaling of CMIP7 GCMs requires a long-term and substantial effort of the WG and of the whole regional ocean climate modelling community. We list here the tasks to be achieved:

CMIP7 Data Request:

The CMIP data request is a list of GCM output variables, along with their frequencies, aggregation methods, and associated metadata that CMIP experiments should save. This step is crucial for any regional climate initiative, as GCM output serves as the primary input for downscaling. Mimicking what is usually done by CORDEX for every CMIP cycle, the TF has submitted a list of variables/frequencies to be stored and shared by the CMIP7 modelling center from a selected set of ScenarioMIP experiments, along with the historical CMIP experiment. Using previous experience of the TF members, this list took care of both the request to force coupled RCMs and the request to force ocean-forced RCMs, including ocean physics, biogeochemistry and sea-ice components. This action was led by A. Melet in Fall 2024 and has been coordinated with the CORDEX-CMIP7 TF.

In CMIP7, the DR is divided into 5 thematic areas. Each thematic area collected opportunities, that is, science enabled by the requested variables which is essential for a given MIP or user group. As CORDEX, the TF-Ocean DR lies under the Impacts & Adaptation thematic area (Ruane et al., 2025), where the opportunities were collected by means of a [Mural board](#), as an intermediate step for the thematic author team to fill the final [Airtable database](#)¹ of Opportunities, Variable groups, Variables or Physical parameters. At the time of writing, the CMIP7 DR is in version 1.2.2, released on Jul 25th, 2025². The follow-up to this action will be handled hand-by-hand with the new CORDEX-CMIP7 TF.

Coordinated experiment design

Following CORDEX-CMIP7 TF, we define a coordinated experiment design document as *“the minimum set of instructions to coordinate the simulations carried out in the different regional domains. It is laid out in a document where mandatory and recommended practices are established regarding, for example, the simulation periods to be covered, the GHG scenarios to be used as forcing, the minimal spatial resolution, etc. Regional communities can adopt the experiment design as is or adapt it for their purposes; but always towards being more restrictive. That is, mandatory instructions should not be*

¹ https://bit.ly/CMIP7-DReq-v1_2

² <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip7-data-request-v1-2-2>

relaxed." The experiment design should follow the FAIR principles and being accessible, well-identified, and versioned. Zenodo seems to be the right platform to host such documents.

Defining a coordinated experimental protocol is key to fostering discussions, mutual understanding, and engagement within the modelling community in multi-model coordinated initiatives. Following coordinated protocols brings confidence in the produced simulations and allows more robust multi-model assessments. Since model uncertainty is one of the major sources of uncertainty in future climate projections (Hawkins and Sutton, 2009; Evin et al., 2021), following a common experimental protocol also allows to disentangle each specific source of uncertainty in forthcoming multi-model analyses.

To our knowledge, coordinated official experiment design dedicated to regional ocean climate projections are currently very rare and adapted to specific domains (e.g. Somot et al. 2024, Med-CORDEX Baseline run protocol). The WG will therefore need to develop community-coordinated regional ocean climate modelling experiment design to foster building of quality-assessed regional ocean model ensemble and intercomparisons. It is likely that two simulation protocols will have to be developed, one for coupled RCMs, close to CORDEX experiment design and one for ocean-forced RCMs. We will have to investigate if a third protocol is needed for the ocean biogeochemistry component or if it can fit in the previous ones. From the authors past experiences, defining regional climate model protocols is often more difficult than for global models as more external forcings must be specified and therefore agreed upon by the modelling participants; this is particularly challenging for regional marine biogeochemical modelling. To define a common protocol for a Regional Ocean Climate Projections initiative, various choices should be made, considering the diversity of the ocean regions. This includes at least (1) the minimal content of the model configurations (including coupling) also called level of complexity or comprehensiveness, (2) the minimal domain to be covered, (3) the minimal spatial (horizontal/vertical) and temporal resolution of the models, (4) the socio-economic and climate change driving scenario(s), (5) the driving GCMs, (6) the list of the other mandatory forcings (river, lateral ocean boundary conditions, aerosol-informed radiation, chlorophyll, ...), (7) the choice of the minimal running time period, (8) the minimal ensemble size, (9) the initialization and spin-up strategy, (10) the acceptance or not of a priori bias-corrections or nudging techniques as well as (11) the archive specification (file format, metadata, data request).

In addition, this protocol will have to align with other existing protocols such as CMIP7 ScenarioMIP, CORDEX-CMIP7, CMIP7-OMIP, COWCLIP or ISIMIP7 (e.g. FishMIP) to ensure the availability of forcings for regional ocean climate simulations and to provide the expected outputs to the whole climate modelling chain from scenario to impacts and

adaptation. We are aware that getting an experimental protocol approved by the participants will take time, probably various generations of the runs and will require flexibility, that can be translated by wording such as “mandatory”, “strongly recommended”, “recommended”, “welcome” all along the protocol text.

On the longer-term, coordinated experiment protocols for statistical models based on machine learning approaches will be developed, trying as much as possible to converge with the physics-based protocols. The capacity of ML-based models to deliver reliable future projections must be first demonstrated.

Coordinated evaluation framework

A coordinated evaluation framework is needed for a robust multi-model assessment and evaluation and includes the choice of a common set of metrics with a common calculation, time period, reference datasets (observations, reanalyses, ...). As for the experimental protocol, a targeted evaluation protocol for regional ocean climate projections will need to be developed to complement existing ones (e.g., CMIP ESMValTool, Rapid Evaluation Framework, CMEMS product quality strategy, Section 2.2). Beyond the multi-model assessment, a coordinated evaluation protocol will allow to assess in a common way across modelling centers the added-value & fitness-for-purpose of regionally downscaled projections, ensuring more robust overall conclusions.

Data request

The data request (DR) is the set of variables, frequencies requested from the modelling groups to be saved in their simulations to allow multi-model studies a posteriori. Lists dedicated to ocean physics, biogeochemistry, wave and sea-ice will have to be developed, blending the CMIP Ocean variables and CORDEX regional approaches. This DR will probably include a CORE list to be stored in all domains and optional variables, specific to domains. Reaching a final agreement for such a list is always difficult as diverging forces are at play. However, a co-design step with a variety of future data users is necessary to avoid missing important applications. In addition, the CORE list should remain limited to open the initiative to modelling groups with less storage capacity. Static fields such as ocean grid mesh characteristics, bathymetry, but also forcing fields (river inputs, air-sea fluxes) will also have to be produced.

Med-CORDEX has produced the first ocean-oriented DR for ocean physics following the CORDEX framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8207552>). The WG will have to investigate if this can serve as a starting point to develop the initiative DR. The development of the DR will have to be strongly coordinated with the new CORDEX-CMIP7 TT.

Archiving specifications

The Archive Specifications gather all information required to produce standardized files and in particular technical details of the file naming, structure and metadata. These rules are essential to guide modeling centers to organize, name, and describe their climate model data so that it can be shared and compared with other model data, especially through publication via the ESGF. The WG will have to investigate if the current CORDEX Archive specifications are already adapted to regional ocean and coupled models or if they need adaptations. Whatever, coordination with the TT CORDEX-CMIP7 will be needed. Note that so far, none of the CORDEX domains have published ocean variables on the ESGF, aside the atmosphere variables.

Data delivery

The final step will be to deliver the data to various targets: (1) the scientific community for science knowledge development, (2) the impact community to drive impact models such as in ISIMIP (including FISHMIP), (3) the IA community to train their statistical models, (4) the climate service community to create society-relevant information from the initiative dataset. This will likely rely on a 2-tier approach with first internal data sharing on a central repository (to be determined) and then publication on an open database such as ESGF.

5.2 Meet the user needs

The success of the initiative will rely on the new knowledge brought by the research community using the produced datasets but also on the capacity to propose datasets relevant to external users, involved in society adaptation to climate change. The second objective requires an early involvement of the potential future users of the data through a series of actions:

Survey of the user needs and co-design

The WG would need to organize dedicated events to increase its knowledge of the potential users of the produced datasets. This can include dedicated surveys over the next years to inform the protocols and the DR for instance, in-person meetings with sectoral specialists, collaborations with RfS, a WCRP core project specialized in user interface or with operational climate services (e.g. C3S, CMEMS), already organized to collect user feedbacks and requests. A first list of user groups includes ocean-oriented climate services, impact and adaptation research community, near-coastal ocean modelling (e.g. the UN Ocean Decade FLAME project and its evolving community of practice for climate downscaling to coastal seas), intermediate users, educational community.

To be successful in the long-term, the coordinated modeling initiative will have to be co-designed with the user groups. Managing this on a global scale, considering the diversity of the users, will constitute a clear challenge for the WG. We have no clear solution to propose yet. The pilots' sites of GlobalCoast (coastpredict.org) provide a potential vehicle for this.

Below, you can find an illustration of a synthesis from the recent stakeholder [survey](#) of the Horizon Europe SEACLIM European project regarding stakeholder's needs on regional ocean climate projections, synthesizing the 789 collected answers. This action has been coordinated by A. Melet.

Figure 3: Illustration of results from the Horizon Europe SEACLIM stakeholder survey on regional ocean climate projections needs, showing the profiles of respondents, sector for which they need regional ocean climate projections, and needed spatial resolution for the different ocean components.

Model documentation, errata service and user guidelines

Models are often seen as black boxes for non-modelers. Description of the models and the simulations in a format understandable and user-friendly is another challenge to be tackled, likely in coordination with the model documentation and errata service in CMIP and CORDEX-CMIP7.

In addition, we envisage to develop a user guideline describing good practices and potential misusages of the regional ocean climate projections, inspired by the EURO-

CORDEX equivalent document
(https://www.euro-cordex.net/imperia/md/content/csc/cordex/guidance_for_euro-cordex_climate_projections_data_use__2021-02_1_.pdf)

User-friendly data access

Publications of climate data on the ESGF is a mandatory step to share data with external users. However, various users do not have the technical capacity to handle such datasets and strategies will have to be developed to facilitate the data access to this category of users. User-friendly web portal such as climate4impact (<https://www.climate4impact.eu/>), the MyOcean Viewer (<https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/viewer/>) or the C3S ERA explorer (<https://era-explorer.climate.copernicus.eu/>), or dedicated sectoral climate services.

5.3 Gathering the community and facilitate new scientific knowledge production

The community concerned by the new proposed initiative is potentially very large as regional ocean models or even coupled RCMs are largely spread tools, easy to adapt to address local scientific questions. A challenge will therefore to gather this community in a single initiative by proposing motivating activities and an efficient scientific network. Another key aspect will be to increase communication and mutual learning between the regional communities, often established since many decades but rarely in contact. The TF has started to collect email addresses of interested scientists in the dedicated emailing list (future-regional-ocean@meteo.fr), that currently includes 44 members. This list could be completed by the institutes who answered the existing simulation survey and can be expanded by connections to other activities such as Coastpredict.org and FishMIP. In addition, we propose that the WG organize the following activities:

- An international workshop : a brainstorming activity has started in the TF led by S. Estrada to propose an international workshop on Regional Ocean Modelling and Climate Projections, potentially organized in 2027. This workshop could be co-sponsored by CORDEX, CLIVAR and other relevant WCRP initiatives.
- Dedicated sessions in large geophysical union assemblies such as AGU or EGU. The TF, jointly with 4 starting European projects, has proposed the session DO42B - Regionally Downscaled Ocean Climate Predictions and Projections (<https://agu.confex.com/agu/osm26/meetingapp.cgi/Session/254304> to the forthcoming Ocean Science Meeting in Glasgow in February 2026. This will be

an opportunity to test the community interest for the WG objectives and to increase the member list of the future-regional-ocean@meteo.fr emailing list.

- A list of publications: to increase the exchange of knowledge between the community, we propose to start a list of publications gathering all relevant studies.
- Special issues could also be proposed, for example, after the international workshop.
- Creation and use of a specific and well-identified hashtag on social media (e.g. #RegionalOceanClimateProjections)

5.4 Links to other CORDEX, CLIVAR and WCRP initiatives

Link to the other CORDEX activities

The activity of the WG will be strongly coordinated with the new CORDEX-CMIP7 TT as already mentioned above. It will also be connected naturally with the CORDEX Domain and CORE activities as various regional ocean climate models will simply add a level of complexity to existing CORDEX RCM configurations. This can be expected at least Med-CORDEX, EURO-CORDEX, Arctic CORDEX, Central America, Australasia, South-East Asia. It is also very likely that the new WG will propose new CORDEX regions centered over large oceanic areas (e.g. in the Pacific or Indian Ocean) not well covered today by CORDEX Domains.

The connection with the TF on ML is less defined today but will certainly develop as bias correction especially at the coast, empirical and statistical downscaling approaches and Machine Learning-based model emulators are currently developing fields of research in oceanography. The connection with the TF-CPM is less clear today as CPRCM domains are currently too small to force or to be coupled to basin-scale ocean models.

The WG will also have to develop strong connections and coordination with the various recent FPS dedicated to the study of islands ([IC-PAC](#), [HighResTC-CAR](#) and [FPS-I-MAC](#)).

Link to RfS

Outside CORDEX, the WG could establish links with the CORE project RfS, in particular to explore the decadal forecast scale, to connect with the science of the climate services and to improve the way to connect with society, one of the specialty of RfS.

Link to CLIVAR

The task force and its activity were presented to the CLIVAR community beyond its Ocean Model Development Panel during the [pan-CLIVAR meeting and its symposium](#) in September 2025. The pan-CLIVAR meeting also gathered representatives from other WCRP core projects and external programmes. Within CLIVAR, joint panel meetings were organized between NORP-SORP-OMDP and GSOP-OMDP, where the activity of the TF and synergies were discussed.

Within the Ocean Model Development Panel, the Ocean Model Intercomparison Project (OMIP) Working Group design and coordinate shared experimental protocols for ocean and sea-ice models to ensure consistency and comparability across modelling centers, to assess how model formulation and parameterization choices affect the simulation of key ocean processes across large-scale and (sub)mesoscale dynamics. The coordinated protocols to be developed by the proposed WCRP Regional Ocean Climate Projections WG could leverage the OMIP experience and protocols.

Link to ESMO and CMIP, ISIMIP

Contacts with ESMO have been already established during the CMIP7 Data Request period. It will certainly continue on multiple topics such as with CMIP for finalizing the DR and for the data delivery, with REF to help selecting the driving GCMs and with OBS4MIP to access high-quality, well-qualified and climate-aware observations.

The TF also met with FishMIP (in ISIMIP) to inform them of the initiative, discuss their need and common interests. The connection with the regional FishMIP activities seems natural to both parties and will certainly continue in the future as FishMIP partners are among the potential users of the WG simulations.

Link to GeWeX

The connection with GeWeX is natural as the ocean is part of the overall water cycle and as this initiative owns a long-term knowledge of key drivers of the ocean such as river discharges, precipitation and evaporation over the sea.

Link to CliC

CliC can bring to our new initiative its sea-ice modelling and observation expertise as well as its network for the polar regions

Link to LightHouse Activities, including Digital Earths, MyClimateRisk

Interactions with at least two of the WCRP LHA are foreseen: (1) MyClimateRisk for investigating the storyline possibilistic approach to deal with climate risks with an ocean focus and for their experience in user involvement starting from the user perspective (2) Digital Earths for their experience in very-high-resolution modelling in the ocean

Link to FLAME

The TF has strong links with the Future Coastal Ocean Climates (FLAME) UN Ocean Decade project, with cross-membership in the respective groups. FLAME is a core project of the coastpredict UND programme, linking it with GlobalCoast. FLAME aims to coordinate best-practice and knowledge sharing, and facilitate end-users interaction for future climate downscaling in the global coastal ocean, across scales and disciplines.

Link to COWCLIP

Concerning wave modelling and related experiment protocol and data request, we plan to coordinate with the COWCLIP ([Coordinated Ocean Wave CLimate Project](#)) initiative, already well experienced in wave modelling and study at climate scales.

6. Timeline

Figure 4: TF and WG timeline, including key dates for IPCC-AR7, CMIP7 and CORDEX

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